

obtained in the reaction of $ZrOCl_2$ melted at 74° and analysed for dichloramine-B (DCB or $RNCl_2$) (Found : Cl, 30.9 ; S, 14.21 ; N, 6.3. Requires Cl, 31.4 ; S, 14.16 ; N, 6.19%).

Results and Discussion

Conductivity titration curves of $AgNO_3$ and $HgCl_2$ with CAB have shown breaks at 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios, respectively, in accordance with the composition in solid state. The stoichiometric equations can be represented as in (1) and (2).

where R is $C_6H_5SO_3$. The uv and ir spectra of CAB, $RNClAg$ and $(RNCl)_2Hg$ are superimposable indicating that they are simple salts.

Similar conductivity titrations of thorium and zirconium solutions against CAB show breaks at 1 : 3 and 1 : 1 molar ratios, respectively. Carefully neutralised solutions of Th^{IV} and Zr^{IV} with NaOH were mixed with CAB, no precipitation was observed. These results indicate that H^+ produced, during the hydrolysis of these ions in aqueous solution is actually involved in the formation of DCB. The hydrolysis equilibria⁴ of Th^{IV} and Zr^{IV} in aqueous solution can be represented by equations (3) and (4).

The precipitate obtained could be dichloramine-B (DCB) which is only sparingly soluble in water. The breaks obtained at 1 : 3 and 1 : 1 molar ratios in conductometric titrations of Th^{4+} and Zr^{4+} with CAB probably indicate the formation of $RNHCl$. The disproportionation reactions of $RNHCl$ has already been reported¹ and are shown in equations (5-7).

The uv and ir spectra of the precipitates and DCB prepared by literature method⁵ were identical confirming the formation of DCB.

Acknowledgement

One of authors (B.N.U.) thanks the U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. H. S. YATHIRAJAN, RANGASWAMY and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1982, 47, 1826.
2. RANGASWAMY, H. S. YATHIRAJAN and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Rev. Rum. Chim.*, 1981, 26, 565.
3. RANGASWAMY, B. N. USHA and H. S. YATHIRAJAN, *Analyst*, 1984, 109, 101.

4. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and RANGASWAMY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 463.
5. H. S. YATHIRAJAN, D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and RANGASWAMY, *Talanta*, 1980, 27, 52.

Intermolecular Attractive Forces at Oil/0.05% Lignosulphonate of *Eucalyptus teriticornis*-Water Interfaces

W. U. MALIK, S. K. SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, Roorkee

TRILOK CHAND*

Institute of Petroleum Exploration, Dehradun

and

SATISH KUMAR and A. K. JINDAL

Institute of Paper Technology, Saharanpur

Manuscript received 17 May 1983, revised 29 May 1984,
accepted 15 August 1984

LITERATURE reveals that surface tension and interfacial tension are the direct measure of intermolecular forces, viz. spreading coefficient, liquid/liquid phase interaction, contact angles, Girifalco-Good's constants¹ etc. The attractive forces at oil/water interfaces between unlike molecules are mainly the dispersion forces²⁻⁵. The surface free energy on the surface layer depends upon the sum of attraction forces present on the surface molecules.

The molecular attraction calculations, between dissimilar molecules are the geometric mean of the dispersion forces of the two sets of molecules. This comes directly from the original prediction of London⁶ and is confirmed for different dissimilar molecules of equal size by studying regular solutions^{7,8}. To evaluate the industrial use of any surface active agent, these parameters are the prerequisite and so the lignosulphonate of *Eucalyptus teriticornis* has been studied from this viewpoint and discussed systematically in this paper.

Experimental

Double-distilled kerosene (sp. gr., 0.7948), turpentine (sp. gr., 0.8745) and water having conductance $10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ were used in all the experiments.

The alcohols, viz. methanol, ethanol, n-propanol, n-butanol pentanol and sodium chloride used were of AnalaR, B.D.H. grade. The lignosulphonate from eucalyptus wood was prepared at Star Paper Mills, Saharanpur and at Cellulose and Paper Branch, Forest Research Institute, Dehradun.

Surface tension: The surface tension, having various formulations of lignosulphonate concentrations, viz., 0.01, 0.02, 0.04, 0.08 and 0.1%, lignosulphonate 0.05%+0.1% v/v alcohols, lignosulphonate 0.05%+NaCl (0.01, 0.02, 0.04, 0.08 and 0.1%), and

lignosulphonate 0.05% at 20, 25, 30, 35 and 40°, has been reported by drop weight method^{9,10}.

Interfacial tension: The interfacial tension data of the above formulations against kerosene oil and turpentine oil have been used from the author's earlier work¹¹. All the experiments were conducted at 25±1°.

Calculations of spreading coefficient, Girifalco-Good's constant and liquid/liquid interface interaction: The spreading coefficient, Girifalco-Good's constant, and liquid/liquid interface interaction of above formulations at kerosene and turpentine oil surfaces have been calculated from the following expressions, respectively¹²

$$S = Y_w - (Y_o + Y_{ow}) \quad (1)$$

$$Y_{ow} = Y_o + Y_w - 2\theta(Y_o \times Y_w)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Liquid/liquid interface interaction} = Y_{ow}^{\text{cal}} - Y_{ow}^{\text{obs}} \quad (3)$$

where S is spreading coefficient; Y_w , surface tension of aqueous phase; Y_o , surface tension of oil phase; Y_{ow} , interfacial tension; θ , Girifalco-Good's constant; Y_{ow}^{cal} , calculated interfacial tension; and Y_{ow}^{obs} , experimental interfacial tension.

The results are presented in Tables 1-3.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF LIGNOSULPHONATE CONCENTRATION ON INTERMOLECULAR FORCES

Lignosulphonate Concn. %	Kerosene oil			Turpentine oil		
	S erg cm ⁻²	ϕ	excess energy	S erg cm ⁻²	ϕ	excess energy
0.01	19.05	0.84	+19.05	23.40	0.87	+23.40
0.02	15.91	0.87	+15.91	22.41	0.93	+22.41
0.04	15.89	0.90	+15.89	21.53	0.96	+21.53
0.08	15.29	0.93	+15.29	20.10	0.97	+20.10
0.10	9.69	0.91	+9.69	14.44	0.95	+14.44

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ALCOHOL-CARBON CHAIN LENGTH Lignosulphonate concn. = 0.05% (w/v) Alcohol concn. = 0.1% (v/v)

Alcohol	Kerosene oil			Turpentine oil		
	S erg cm ⁻²	ϕ	excess energy	S erg cm ⁻²	ϕ	excess energy
CH ₃ OH	25.70	0.96	+25.70	29.80	0.99	+29.80
C ₂ H ₅ OH	7.45	0.89	+7.45	10.95	0.91	+10.95
C ₃ H ₇ OH	20.90	0.82	+20.90	-17.35	0.82	+17.35
C ₄ H ₉ OH	25.55	0.91	+22.55	-22.40	0.89	-22.40
C ₅ H ₁₁ OH	28.35	1.01	-18.35	-25.20	0.98	-25.20

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SALINITY Lignosulphonate concn. = 0.05% (w/v)

NaCl %	Kerosene oil			Turpentine oil		
	S erg cm ⁻²	ϕ	excess energy	S erg cm ⁻²	ϕ	excess energy
0.01	10.11	0.80	+10.11	14.94	0.83	+14.94
0.02	13.56	0.87	+13.56	19.66	0.92	+19.66
0.04	14.13	0.90	+14.13	19.63	0.95	+19.63
0.08	14.37	0.98	+14.37	19.25	0.97	+19.25
0.10	12.27	0.92	+12.77	17.49	0.96	+17.40

Results and Discussion

The results of spreading coefficients presented in Tables 1-3 show that higher lignosulphonate concentration and high temperature, lower the spreading coefficient and hence increase the spreading nature while higher salinity increases the non-spreading nature of aqueous phase containing lignosulphonate. Table 2 depicts that CH₃OH and C₃H₇OH favour spreading nature but for C₄H₉OH to C₅H₁₁OH, the spreading coefficient has negative values, thereby depicting a high cohesion and non-spreading nature.

Girifalco-Good's constant data show that higher concentration of lignosulphonate and salinity favour hydrogen bonding between oil and surfactant solutions while temperature disfavours this phenomenon. This is in agreement with the fact that for hydrogen bond formation in both the liquids, Girifalco-Good's constant must be greater than 0.84 value¹.

The calculated and observed interfacial tension data and liquid-liquid interaction (by assuming only dispersive force interactions at the surface) indicate that with the exception of C₃H₇OH to C₅H₁₁OH, Y_{ow}^{cal} is greater than Y_{ow}^{obs} , the excess energy may be attributed to the interaction between phases.

References

1. L. A. GIRIFALCO and R. J. GOOD, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, **61**, 904.
2. F. M. FOWKES, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 1869.
3. F. M. FOWKES, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 2533.
4. F. M. FOWKES, "Adhesion", ASTM Spec. Tech. Pub., 1964, No. 360.
5. F. M. FOWKES, "Advances in Chemistry", 1964, **43**, 59-111.
6. F. LONDON, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, **8**, 33.
7. J. H. HILDEBRAND and R. L. SOOFT, "Regular Solution", Practice-Hall, Angewood Cliffs, 1962, pp. 79-80.
8. J. H. HILDEBRAND and R. L. SOOFT, "Solubility of Non-electrolytes", 3rd ed., Reinhold, New York, 1950.
9. W. D. HARKINS and F. E. BROWN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **38**, 499.
10. W. D. HARKINS and F. E. BROWN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **41**, 228.
11. W. U. MALIK, S. K. SRIVASTAVA, T. CHAND and A. K. JINDAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 1053.
12. F. M. FOWKES, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1964, **40**, 13, 5c.

Studies on Arndt-Eistert Synthesis : Synthesis of N-Aryl-N'-3-methyl- caproylurea Derivatives

K. R. DESAI and M. M. PATHAK

Department of Chemistry, South Gujarat University,
Surat-395 007

Manuscript received 15 February 1984, revised 24 May 1984,
accepted 10 August 1984

UREA derivatives possess wide therapeutic activity such as antibacterial¹, antithyroid, hypnotic and anesthetic, hypoglycemic², anthelmintic, diuretic³ and biocidal. Phenylacetamidourea derivatives are active anticonvulsants.